

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.	B494		
Date:	07 DEC 2009		
Take Off:	18:31:06Z	Z	Z
Landing:	23:19:57Z	Z	Z
Flight Time:	4:48:51	h m s	h m s

Campaign: RONOCO

Operating Area: London M25 orbits and E coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	Lookout Pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
4	CCM	Robbie Voaden	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist 1	Paul Monks	York
6	Flight Manager / PCASP	Mo Smith	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM
8	WAS 1	James Lee	
9	WAS 2	Richard Lidster	FAAM
10	AMS	James Allan	Manchester
11	BBCEAS 1	Oliver Kennedy	Cambridge
12	BBCEAS 2	Bin Ouyang	Cambridge
13	Peroxide / Formaldehyde	Brian Bandy	East Anglia
14	PTrMS	Dave Oram	East Anglia
15	CIMS 1	Max McGillen	Manchester
16	CIMS	Michael Le Breton	Manchester
17	Mission Scientist 2	Rod Jones	Cambridge
18	Mission Scientist 3	Grant Forster	East Anglia
19			

	Log Sheet included
Y	Flight Folder Front Page
Y	Flight Summary
Y	Met Office 0600 UTC Actual Surface analysis (ASXX) chart
Y	Track Plot (GIN or GPS)
	DFLFliteStar planned track
Y	Brief
	Mission Scientist 1's logs
	Mission Scientist 2's logs
Y	De-brief
	ViRC chat log
Y	Flight Manager's Instrument Status log
Y	Flight Manager's Faults/Incidents log
	Pre-flight log
	Core Chemistry / NOx / TDLAS
	Cloud Physics In Flight
	Cloud Physics Processing
	AVAPS
	PSAP log
	Filters
	Printed Plots
	Screengrabs
	Planning charts or plots
	Images Emailed To BAe146 In Flight

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	2009-12-11	Mo Smith	Initial version
R1			
r2			

RONOCO Sorties

Sortie 1 – Round London, Southend, Thames Estuary, N. Norfolk coast

Outline

The aim of RONOCO is to explore night-time chemistry under a range of pollutant loadings. The winter trials will explore operating requirements and also try to map night-time pollutants with a view to more detailed studies at a later date.

The aim of sortie 1 is to explore night-time pollution gradients around a strong emission source (i.e. London) and down-wind in the Thames estuary area and off the Suffolk/Norfolk Coast.

Much of the execution of the science of the flights will be conducted at minimum safe altitude with the missed approaches at nearby airports used to give a profile through the atmosphere and verify the position of the boundary layer.

Sortie 1 – Monday 7th December

EVEB73 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 07 Dec 2009 1500 UTC

15.00 UTC satellite image

Sortie 1: London-Southend-Norfolk

#	approx time	approx altitude	detail
(1)		take off	Take off and ascend to FL100, with short hold for wet chemistry checks
(2)		10,000 ft	Manoeuvre to allow 10 mins calibration for NO _x at FL100, before (3)
(3)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach
(4)		ascend	Ascend to <i>minimum safe altitude</i>
(5)		MSA	Perform one complete anti-clockwise circuit of the city at this level
(6)		descend	Descend into Northolt airport and perform a missed approach (if possible given airfield timing)
(7)		MSA	Perform another circuit finishing at Southend with a missed approach
(8)		descend	Climb to 5,000ft (up to 10,000ft if poss.) and transit to East Coast
(9)		MSA	Science speed at MSA to safe distance off coast to achieve nautical MSA and measure off coast travelling in a northwards direction as far as time permits to the north. (there maybe a want for shallow profiles i.e. MSA to 5,000ft if possible.)
(10)		MSA	Recover to EMA at lowest possible altitude over land (before executing (11))
(11)		10,000ft	Allow 10 mins for NO _x cal before landing at FL100

EGTC -> EGNX - Overview

NavData Cycle 2009.12 Expires: Thursday, 17 December 2009.
Scale: 1:1831667 (1 inch = 25.12 naut mi). Printed on 04 Dec 2009

76996 ; 68

FliteStar 9.4.7.0

Outline Flight Plans

B494 Outline (7th Dec 2009)

The aim of RONOCO is to explore night-time chemistry under a range of pollutant loadings. The winter trials will explore operating requirements and also try to map night-time pollutants with a view to more detailed studies at a later date.

The aim of sortie 1 is to explore night-time pollution gradients around a strong emission source (i.e. London) and down-wind in the Thames estuary area and off the Suffolk/Norfolk Coast.

Mission Science Notes

There was a frontal system passing across the UK in a west-east direction during the course of 7th December 2009. The aim of the sortie was to get behind this frontal system in the westerly flow and map the pollution round London and off the east coast. On this occasion the meteorology behaved well.

Tephigrams at take off and the 1st missed approach into Northolt showed a relatively deep well mixed layer to a height of around 2,400 ft or so. The first track round London was relatively clean until we got due east of the city centre when the top of the London Plume was intercepted. Both Northolt missed approaches showed a quite polluted boundary layer with NO_x in the orders of 10s ppbV. In the boundary layer there were mixed aerosol signatures.

The pollution was again observed at Southend, the decision was made to transit out into the North Sea and head South to resample the London plume off the Thames estuary area to the top of the English channel. It was clear the operating at MSA over the sea, we were well within the boundary layer. On the northward return from the south, the London plume was intercepted again. This was a wide persistent feature. Given the nature of the interception, there is a possibility of a pseudo-lagrangian analysis as we have upwind London, near-side London and down-wind London. The wind was about 10 ms⁻¹ from the west during the bulk of the flight.

After a brief sojourn at 10,000ft the aircraft descended to MSA to run up the coast to north of Flamborough head. There was an amazing number of plumes, clear distinct and also of varying chemical composition. This bodes well for the goal of RONOCO to map chemical gradients in the atmosphere. The AMS and new NO_x instrument were picking up these changes and at times O₃ was reduced to single figures in the some of these plumes. The situation was reproducible on the return leg to Blakeney.

Instrument Overview

BBCEAS – first flight – data collected well at MSA, less at higher altitude, first spectral look promising

WAS – 64 bottles filled
PTR – failed communication

All other instruments were nominal.

PSM/RLJ (Mission Scientists)

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B494

Date: 7 December 2009

Project: RONOCO

Location: M25 and SE coast

Start End

Time	Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
173753		Start-Up	0.84 kft	355	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
182655		ASP&AMS	0.83 kft	173	Open
183106		T/O	2.3 kft	284	Cranfield
183847	184951	Run 1	10.0 kft	036	NOx Cal
184956	185543	Profile 1	10.0 - 2.9 kft	242	
185544	190544	Run 2	2.9 - 2.8 kft	174	2.4k' on QNH 996mb
190544	191038	Profile 1	2.8 - 0.65 kft	249	2.4k'-50' over Northolt
191038	191314	Profile 2	0.65 - 2.9 kft	248	Northolt 50'-2.4k'
191314	195222	Run 3	2.9 - 2.7 kft	329	2.4k'
191510		Heimann	2.9 kft	252	Cal
192109			2.9 kft	041	WP C
194048		Event	2.9 kft	207	WP A
192901		Event	2.9 kft	041	WP C
194048		Event	2.9 kft	097	WP B
193600		Event	2.9 kft	041	WP C
194048		Event	2.9 kft	358	WP D
194400		Event	2.9 kft	344	In Cloud
194513		Event	2.9 kft	316	WP E
195339	195627	Profile 3	2.5 - 0.62 kft	252	2k'-50',Q996 ,Northolt
195627	195842	Profile 4	0.62 - 2.5 kft	247	50-2.0k'
195843	200113	Run 4	2.5 kft	275	2.0k'
200040		Event	2.5 kft	248	WP F
200113	200137	Profile 5	2.7 - 2.9 kft	243	
200137	203600	Run 5	2.9 kft	241	2.4k'-50'
200252			2.9 kft	232	2.4k', Q998
200606		Event	2.9 kft	209	WP A
201033		Heimann	2.9 kft	151	Cal
201404		Event	2.8 kft	127	WP B
202130		Event	2.8 kft	065	WP C
202647		Event	2.8 kft	356	WP D
203135		Event	2.8 kft	032	WP E
203600	203705	Profile 6	2.9 - 2.0 kft	037	2.4k'-50'
204044	204243	Profile 6	2.0 - 0.51 kft	235	Southend 1.5k-50'
204244	204537	Profile 7	0.51 - 3.8 kft	234	3.4k'
204555	204759	Run 6	3.9 kft	047	3.4k'
204800	205009	Profile 7	3.9 - 5.9 kft	049	5.4k'

205023	210019	Run 7	5.9 - 2.1 kft	050 5.4k' -
210019	210028	Profile 8	2.1 kft	193 -
210028	213804	Run 8	2.1 - 1.9 kft	192 1.5k, Q993
210630		Heimann	1.9 kft	202 Cal
211036		Event	1.9 kft	193 WP 42
211102		Event	1.9 kft	134 Turn reciprocal
212150		Event	1.9 kft	009 Into a plume
212504		Event	2.0 kft	006 WP 41
212810		Event	1.9 kft	016 Out of the plume
213452		Event	2.0 kft	357 Precipitation
213805	214301	Profile 9	1.9 - 6.5 kft	357 1.5k, Q993
214146		Event	5.3 kft	279 WP 40
214301	215850	Run 9	6.5 - 6.4 kft	277
215850	220336	Profile 10	6.4 - 2.0 kft	156 1.5k', Q996
220345	225143	Run 10	2.0 kft	313
220802		Event	2.0 kft	327 Plume
222241		Event	2.0 kft	332 WP 80
222650		Event	2.0 kft	309 Turn reciprocal
223149		Event	2.0 kft	152 WP 80
225445	230805	Run 11	10.0 kft	218 NOx Cal
231957		Land	0.68 kft	216 East Midlands
232331		Shutdown	0.68 kft	298 52'49.65N, 1'20.28W
232343		ASP	0.68 kft	298 Closed

asxx 07/12/2009 18:00 UTC

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B494

Date: 07 Dec 09

Instruments

1. Nevz TWC zeros okay but signal output always flatlines (at 0uA on control unit meter). DLU reading always 6346 DRSU.
2. PTrMS – no communication between pc and instrument
3. Video – temporary Ethernet cable between CC aft and hub to get video to the recorder laptop.
4. CCN – shortcut missing from FM desktop
5. Buck – recording program crashed pre-flight (blue screen). Tried restarting it but it just flashed up and closed. Recorded it via Hyperterminal, okay.
6. Rosemount temps – about 2degC difference (at ~6C)
7. BBCEAS – comms problems, can't see one of the laptops on network but got some data and working on landing.
8. BBCEAS – need harness points and intercom box on rack

Core Chem – good

AMS – some software glitches but otherwise okay

Peroxide & Formaldehyde –good

CIMS – worked well but nothing to see (washed out by rain)

WAS – filled 64 bottles

PAN – okay but nothing to see

Aircraft

1. Cockpit door got jammed, possibly accidentally locked from inside.

Satcom

MPDS – connected on VIRC but kept dropping out so stopped using it 2010Z

Satcom H – 1 call received from PC

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Choose A Flight Number To Show Instrument Status For It

Choose Flight

[back](#)

Key :

	Not Operated		
	Minor Problems		
	Ok		

B494

Primary Systems

- AMTG
- AVAPS
- Cabin Pressure Rmount
- Camera - Downward Facing
- Camera - Forward Facing
- Camera - Rearward Facing
- Camera - Upward Facing
- Cruciform GPS
- DLU AERACK
- DLU BBR Lower
- DLU BBR Upper
- DLU Core Chem
- DLU Core Consoles
- DLU Port Aft
- DLU Port Fwd
- DLU Stbd Fwd
- Fax machine
- GIN Applanix POSAV510
- HORACE
- INU Honeywell H423
- Printer
- Radar Altimeter
- RVSM IAS
- RVSM Static Pressure
- S9 Static Press Rmount
- Satcom Phones
- Satcom Data
- Turb Diff Centre-Static
- Turb Diff Left-Right
- Turb Diff Up-Down
- Turb Horizontal Check
- Turb Vertical Check
- Weather Radar
- XR5 GPS

Temperature

- Cabin Temperature
- Heimann
- Rosemount DIT
- Rosemount NDIT

Hygrometry

- Buck CR2
- FWVS
- General Eastern
- Total Water Probe
- SAW Hygrometer

Remote Sensing

- BBR (clear) Lower
- BBR (clear) Upper
- BBR (IR) Lower
- BBR (IR) Upper
- BBR (red) Lower
- BBR (red) Upper
- ARIES
- CASI/ATM
- DEIMOS
- IR Camera
- JNO2 Photometer Lower
- JNO2 Photometer Upper
- JO1D Photometer Lower
- JO1D Photometer Upper
- LIDAR
- MARSS
- Mini-LIDAR
- SHIMS Lower
- SHIMS Upper
- SWS
- TAFTS

Cloud Physics

- 2DC
- 2DP
- FFSSP
- Johnson Williams
- Nevzorov
- 2DS
- ADA
- CAPS
- CDP (Canister)
- CDP (Fuselage)
- CIP 100
- CIP 25
- CPI
- INC
- SID1
- SID2
- SID3

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A
- CPC 3786 H2O
- Filters 47mm
- Filters 90mm
- Nephelometer - Dry
- Nephelometer - Wet
- PCASP
- PCASP SPP-200
- PSAP
- AMS
- CCN
- CPC 3010A
- CPC (AMS)
- CVI Inlet
- CVI PCASP-X
- CVI Ly-A Hygro
- LTI
- SMPS
- SP2
- UHSAS
- VACC

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002
- NOx TE42C
- Ozone TE49
- Ozone TE49C
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4 channel
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2 channel
- CIMS
- FAGE
- Formaldehyde
- NOx FAAM
- NOxy
- ORAC
- PAN
- PERCA
- Peroxide
- PTRMS
- QCL
- SO2 TE43C
- TDLAS (1C)
- WAS Bags
- WAS Bottles

Upper BBRs	
1	clear pyranometer
2	RED Pyranometer
3	JN02
4	JO1D

Rear Cargo Hold			
WAS 1	fitted	WAS 2	fitted
WAS 3	fitted	WAS 4	fitted
WAS 5	fitted	WAS 6	fitted
WAS 7	fitted	CASI/mini-LIDAR	not fitted
ATM	not fitted	Heimann	fitted

Starboard Wing Pylon

Port Wing Pylon

Frame No.: 19 19A 19B 19C 19D 20 22 24 25 26 28 30 32 33 33A 33B 33C 33D 34 36 38 40
 Window No.: 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12 14 16 18 20 22 24 26 28

Diagram 1 of 2: Interior & Forward View
 Title: MCCM Config 9 Var 1 CIMS / RONOCO
 Filename: MCCM Config 9 Var 1 CIMS / RONOCO Diagram 1 of 2
 Date: 07/12/09 Author: S Cowan

Flight No.	Date	Author

Air Sample Pipe
 Inlet: Inlet
 Exhaust: Exhaust
 Pipe: Pipe
 Manifold: Manifold

General Exhausts
 Exhaust: Exhaust
 Pipe: Pipe
 Manifold: Manifold

Dedicated Exhausts
 Exhaust: Exhaust
 Pipe: Pipe
 Manifold: Manifold

Legend:
 S2 Sidewall Service Point
 DLU DLU
 Blanked Window

Scale (Approx.)
 0 1 2 4 6 Feet
 0 1 2 Metres

Diagram 2 of 2: Aircraft Exterior Views

Title: MCCM Config 9 Var 1 CIMS / RONOCO

Filename: MCCM Config 9 Var 1 CIMS / RONOCO Diagram 2 of 2

Date: 07/12/2009 **Author: S Cowan**

Flight No.	Date	Author